

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-12

Passive dew condensation
system for supplementary
irrigation: “Kouloura Flower”

//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Passive dew condensation system for supplementary vineyard irrigation

INPUTS

Ambient air humidity (water vapor), nocturnal radiative cooling conditions

OUTPUTS

Low-salinity condensate water for localized supplementary irrigation of grapevines

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 5

CONTEXT & SCALE

Small-scale, plant-level application in traditionally rainfed vineyards under Mediterranean climate conditions

KEY BENEFITS

Supplementary water supply during dry periods; improved water availability for vines; increased resilience of rainfed viticulture; directing of rainfall towards the root zone

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Dependence on suitable microclimatic conditions (night-time cooling, humidity, wind); limited volumes of recovered water; need for wind-stable design under exposed conditions

CATEGORY

Atmospheric water condensation

//02. WHAT IT IS

The “Kouloura Flower” is a passive atmospheric water condensation system designed to provide localized supplementary irrigation for grapevines trained in the traditional “Kouloura” (basket) style, in rainfed vineyards. It harvests water vapor from the air by condensing moisture on surfaces that are passively cooled below the dew point through nocturnal infrared radiation under clear sky.

The system is installed around the individual vines. Condensed water flows toward the center of the structure and is delivered directly to the vine’s root zone, supporting plant water availability during dry periods without the need for active irrigation infrastructure.

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//03. WHY IT MATTERS

Traditionally rainfed vineyards in Mediterranean island environments are increasingly exposed to prolonged summer droughts and heat stress, while often lacking irrigation infrastructure.

By providing localized supplemental water directly to the vine root zone, the Kouloura Flower can support plant water availability during dry periods without altering traditional cultivation practices.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

The Kouloura Flower is a ground-mounted, passive dew condensation system installed around individual grapevines trained in the traditional Kouloura form. The system is based on a funnel-shaped configuration of planar condensation panels arranged around the vine and inclined at approximately 30°, with one side left open to allow access for vineyard operations. The structure has an outer diameter of approximately 1.5 m and a central opening of about 0.5 m. An inclination of around 30° is typically applied as an optimal balance between maximising radiative cooling performance (which is highest at 0°) and providing sufficient slope to ensure reliable condensate runoff.

The panels consist of an insulating polystyrene (XPS) layer coated with a highly infra-red-emissive surface to enhance nocturnal radiative cooling and promote condensation. The coating is a special customized mix of acrylic paint and highly IR emissive pigments [1]. The overall footprint is adapted to local vine spacing (approximately 1.80 × 1.80 m), enabling plant-level installation without interfering with existing vineyard layouts.

Due to the panels' inclination, condensed water flows inward to provide localized supplementary irrigation directly to the vine's root zone.

Schematic illustration of a passive dew condensation system for supplementary irrigation: "Kouloura Flower" © ANRI 2025

//05. HOW IT WORKS

The system passively condenses water vapour from the air by cooling the panel surfaces below the dew point through nocturnal infrared radiation of the highly IR radiative surface towards the clear sky. Under suitable microclimatic conditions (low wind, not too low dew point), moisture from the air condenses on the panel surfaces.

The condensed water flows by gravity towards the center of the structure and is delivered directly to the vine's root zone, providing localized supplemental irrigation. In addition, the structure guides rainfall towards the central plant, increasing water availability during precipitation events.

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

The Kouloura Flower operates passively under suitable night-time conditions and does not require energy input or active control. Basic visual checks ensure the panels re-

main correctly positioned and free of obstructions, and excess dirt, allowing effective condensation and runoff toward the vine root zone.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Water recovery depends on clear sky and suitable microclimatic conditions, particularly sufficient night-time cooling, air humidity, and low wind disturbance, which influence dew formation. As a result, the system is intended to provide supplementary rather than primary irrigation.

Reliable performance requires appropriate installation and wind-stable design to ensure that condensation surfaces remain effective under exposed vineyard conditions.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

Traditionally rainfed vineyards in Mediterranean and island climates where sufficient night-time cooling, frequent clear nocturnal sky and ambient air humidity enables passive dew formation. The solution is particularly suited to locations seeking low-impact, plant-level supplemental irri-

gation that preserves traditional cultivation systems.

Within the GEORGIA project, this solution is implemented [in a vineyard cultivating the local Assyrtiko grape variety on the island of Santorini, Greece.](#)

//09. KEYWORDS

Dew condensation; Passive water harvesting; Vineyard application; Plant-level irrigation; Supplementary irrigation

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

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//10. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

1. International Organization For Dew Utilization.

Webpage: <https://www.opur.cloud/>

2. D. Beysens, "The formation of dew" Atmospheric Research, Vol. 39, 1-3, p. 215-237, 1995.

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3. M. Muselli, D. Beysens, J. Marcillat, I. Milimouk, T. Nilsson "Dew water collector for potable water in Ajaccio (Corsica Island, France)" Atmospheric Research. Vol. 64, 1-4, p. 297-312, 2002.

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4. D. Beysens, I. Milimouk, V. Nikolayev, M. Muselli "Using radiative cooling to condense atmospheric vapor: a study to improve water yield. Journal of Hydrology", Vol. 276, 1-4, p. 1-11, 2003.

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